

GOOD PRACTICE DIRECTORY FOR CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR

Agro2Circular

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The agri-food industry is one of the most exposed sectors to sustainability challenges and opportunities, due to its reliance on and direct impact on natural resources. As such, it is considered a high-impact industry. Sustainability—social, economic, and environmental—is a fundamental parameter for businesses. Additionally, the agri-food sector plays a key role in transitioning to circular production and consumption models, serving as a pillar for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined in the United Nations' 2030 Agenda. The Agro2Circular project (A2C European project - No 101036838) has planned actions to assist and raise awareness among the agri-food sector regarding the need to apply Circular Economy (CE) principles and achieve these goals.

In this context, AGROFOOD MURCIA has defined a line of work to develop a Directory of Best Practices in Circular Economy associated with the agri-food sector (DBPCE). This directory includes practices developed within the A2C project, as well as successful examples identified through open searches at the National and International levels or via information exchange with stakeholders involved in the project.

Each of the sections of the proposed document was selected with a clear objective of being a quick visualization of the current situation and of the future potential of the revalorization of agri-food by-products and other waste.

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It is based on maintaining the value of resources in the economy for as long as possible. It is a model of production and consumption that involves sharing, leasing, reusing, repairing, renewing and recycling existing materials and products. Thus, it proposes three principles of sustainability:

1. Preserve and enhance natural capital
2. Optimize the greatest circulation of resources
3. Minimize losses and negative impacts

All of this promotes economic growth, social well-being and respect for the environment.

Eco-innovation

This theme is linked to the mission of sustainable business development, so those actions in which the agri-food industry and its auxiliaries work to ensure that the economy has low carbon emissions and an efficient use of energy and resources, innovating in the use of efficient equipment, reduction of the use of raw materials, recycling, valorisation of by-products and application in other sectors, etc., must be considered.

To achieve BPCE status, an action must focus on a series of interconnected principles inherent to the definition of EC itself. These principles, which mark the basis for entities to adopt their practices in the transition to CE, are:

1. **Systemic and holistic thinking:** perception and analysis of reality in a global way, “thinking globally to act locally”.
2. **Responsibility:** assume responsibility (social, economic and environmental) for the impacts resulting from decisions and activities of each action. Educate, raise awareness and sensitize on EC as part of this responsibility.
3. **Rethink/Regenerate:**renew current models in all areas of action (design, production, consumption, use, business, waste management, etc.) to contribute, directly or indirectly, to the transition to CE. Restore and recover the quality of degraded ecosystems, give value to natural capital.
4. **Innovate and virtualize:**promoting R&D&I in the field of EC, working on the replacement of unidirectional, single-use or non-renewable materials, products and resources with more circular and sustainable ones. Direct or indirect dematerialization.
5. **Optimize:**reduction and more efficient use of resources (materials, water and energy). Increase the useful life and performance of products.
6. **“Closing the circle”or “closing the life cycle”** of resources, products and waste: reuse, repair/remodel, remanufacture (use of secondary raw materials), recover (obtaining secondary raw materials and critical materials), recycle and revalue.
7. **Share and collaborate:**new models of consumption, use and collaborative business. Synergy between all the agents involved.
8. **Communication and transparency:**Transmit information in a clear, accurate, timely, honest and complete manner, if possible based on certification standards and eco-labels.

The UN General Assembly adopted in September 2015 the **Agenda 2030** for Sustainable Development. This is an action plan for people, the planet and prosperity, which also aims to strengthen universal peace and access to justice.

To achieve these goals, governments, businesses and civil society must show great involvement and commitment. **Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)** aim to guide the actions of society in general to achieve improvements in the sustainable development of all countries, both developed and developing. The 2030 Agenda sets out 17 Goals with 169 targets of an integrated and indivisible nature that cover the economic, social and environmental spheres.

 SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

The agri-food sector, the plastics sector and the Circular Economy

The agri-food sector, the plastics sector and the circular economy are interconnected in their role in addressing global sustainability challenges. Agri-food by-products and waste are a valuable source of resources due to the presence of compounds of interest that can be transformed or extracted for use in various sectors, as well as their potential as raw material in other processes.

On the one hand, the valorisation of agri-food by-products allows the transformation of waste such as fruit peels, seeds and cereal bran to develop new natural ingredients for the food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries. These by-products are rich in bioactive compounds, such as antioxidants, fibres and proteins, which offer functional and nutritional benefits. This approach not only improves resource efficiency, but also aligns with the principles of the circular economy, promoting innovation and sustainability. On the other hand, they have the potential to be transformed into valuable resources, such as bioplastics or bioenergy, reducing dependence on fossil fuels. This second approach is aligned with the need to design recyclable materials, adopt biodegradable alternatives and minimise waste to move the plastics sector from a linear “extract-make-dispose” model to a circular one.

Furthermore, collaboration between these sectors is vital. For example, agri-food waste can serve as raw material for bioplastics, creating a symbiotic relationship. Furthermore, packaging innovations such as compostable materials reduce plastic pollution while ensuring food safety. Together, these sectors can drive sustainable growth, reduce environmental impact and foster resilience in supply chains.

Current Situation: Policies and Support Programmes for Circular Economy in the Region of Murcia

Several entities in the Region of Murcia are involved in promoting the Circular Economy. CARM (Autonomous Community of the Region of Murcia) plays a significant role through various ministries and instruments, such as the Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia ([https://www.carm.es/web/pagina?IDCONTENIDO=58106&IDTIPO=100&RESULTADO_INFERIOR=11&RESULTADO_SUPERIOR=18&RASTRO=c64\\$m](https://www.carm.es/web/pagina?IDCONTENIDO=58106&IDTIPO=100&RESULTADO_INFERIOR=11&RESULTADO_SUPERIOR=18&RASTRO=c64$m)). This strategy includes 24 action lines, such as the Development of the Bioeconomy (LA 02) and the Promotion of R&D focused on Circular Economy (LA 18). Other relevant instruments include:

- EU Circular Economy Strategy
- Farm to Fork Strategy
- Spanish Circular Economy Strategy “Spain 2030”
- Waste Plan of the Region of Murcia 2016–2020 (extended until 2022)
- Law 7/2022 on Waste and Contaminated Soils for a Circular Economy
- Future Plan Recircula 2027–2035 for Waste Management in the Region of Murcia
- Programme Region of Murcia ERDF 2021–2027 (approved in December 2022)
- Spain’s Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan (PERTE Agri-food and Urban–Rural Agenda)
- Strategic Plan for the CAP 2023–2027 (PEPAC), which includes intervention 7161 aimed at promoting rural development through the circular bioeconomy
- Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart and Sustainable Specialization (RIS4) of the Region of Murcia

The Region of Murcia is working towards sustainable development through various ministries:

- Ministry of Environment, Universities, Research, and the Mar Menor, through the General Directorate of the Environment
- Ministry of Economy, Finance, European Funds, and Digital Transformation, through the General Directorate of Budgets and European Funds
- Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock, and Fisheries, through the General Directorate of Food Industry and Agrarian Associations
- Ministry of Business, Employment, and Social Economy, through the General Directorate of Trade Promotion, Business Innovation, and Artisan Industries, as well as the Development Agency of the Region of Murcia (INFO Murcia)

Methodology for Selecting Best Practices in Circular Economy

Throughout the execution of the European Agro2Circular project, an International diagnosis has been carried out to collect Good Practices of Circular Economy within the agri-food sector and other auxiliary sectors that may benefit from circular developments.

The research has been carried out in the databases of R&D&I projects financed by entities such as Autonomous Communities, CDTI, AEI, H2020, Horizon Europe, etc. that have recently been carried out by Research Centers and Universities, Technology Centers and Companies in collaboration. Once the "Success Story" was located, the website of these entities was searched further and published news was viewed to learn more about them. In this way, the contents of the different files have been completed.

The information collection was carried out in the period October 2022 - September 2024. In total, 75 files have been made available for review and evaluation. Once reviewed, a classification was made into 6 subcategories.

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Packaging

Textile: fashion and footwear

Nutraceutical - Cosmetic

General Platforms

Others

Methodology for Selecting Best Practices in Circular Economy

The selection assessment criteria were:

- Key results: main achievements (environmental, economic and social) achieved with the implementation of the Good Practice. (40%)
- Difficulties or challenges identified (30%)
- Scope of action of the Good Practice – i) agri-food sector; ii) nutraceutical, iii) plastic/packaging, iv) cosmetics, v) others. (20%)
- Link with SDG commitments. (10%)

In this document, 30 Good Practices have been made available to the sector, which include a high percentage of those "Success Stories" most closely linked to the agri-food sector and related to the implementation of the Agro2Circular project on this topic. These are examples that can currently be followed by entities, but not exclusive to the fruit and vegetable subsector, since the document prepared aims to promote replicability between subsectors such as cereals, meat, etc. In summary, a total of 20 specific Good Practices have been obtained from entities linked to the agri-food sector, while another 10 are transversal or from auxiliary sectors.

Best Practices in Circular Economy AGRIFOOD SECTOR

Indulleida

Location: Catalonia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

This company located in Alguaire (Lleida) is dedicated to the production of juices using as raw material fruit and vegetable products that do not meet the specifications for sale.

Key results:

The company was founded in the 1980s as an association of cooperatives and fruit and vegetable centres to dispose of fruit that was not suitable for the fresh market or was surplus and could not be consumed by consumers.

Its philosophy is based on the circular economy, taking advantage of natural resources and reducing energy and water consumption.

BPCE Principles

SDG Objectives

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Potential income • Recovery and utilization of waste • Sustainable development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturing process • Quality issues • Access to finance • Price volatility • Absence of legal standards and definitions

Links

<https://indulleida.com/empresa/>

<https://inovalabs.es/es/5-casos-de-exito-de-economia-circular-en-alimentacion/>

Cynara

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

CYNARA is an artichoke specialist. At Cynara, they offer attractive, creative and different solutions, committed to a 360° innovation model, which allows them to control and optimise all the phases of the process, from the source to the table.

Key results:

CYNARA has launched “Artichoke Chys”, a healthy snack to take advantage of artichoke waste, with a view to expanding business lines beyond canned vegetables, in accordance with current consumer habits.

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Recovery and utilization of waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product acceptance by consumers • Quality issues • Manufacturing process

Links

<https://cynara.net/>

Biodiverso Cosmetics

Nutraceutical - Cosmetic

Location: Murcia (Spain)

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Description and objectives:

Cosmetics company that manufactures different lines of skin care products.

Key results:

One in five fruits and vegetables is rejected for not meeting the aesthetic standards required by supermarkets. The company seeks to address this challenge through more efficient use of natural resources, revaluing by-products and promoting a circular economy model to reduce this waste.

Biodiverso produces cosmetics, specifically body creams, based on fruits and vegetables that do not meet the aesthetic criteria of supermarkets. These products contain 25% of real pulp from these imperfect fruits, helping to give them a new value.

BPCE Principles

SDG Objectives

Links

<https://biodiversocosmetic.com/>

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling of by-products • Recovery and utilization of waste • Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturing process • High initial investments • Access to finance • Product acceptance by consumers

App 'TOO GOOD TO GO'

General Platforms

Location: Denmark (start)

Description and objectives:

Internet retailing of food waste generated by the service sector at a reduced price to avoid food waste.

This is a free mobile app where leftovers from restaurants and shops are put up for sale. This helps reduce food waste, which is currently one of the global problems that most affect the environment.

Key results:

The app has attracted more than 9.5 million users. More than 17,000 establishments have joined the app, saving 10,092,382 food packages.

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.toogoodtogo.com/es>

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sensitization• Cooperation• Food utilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Price volatility• Quality issues

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Väcka

Location: Catalonia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Vegetable cheeses made with fermented milk from melon seeds and extra virgin olive oil. The fermentation of melon seeds provides aromas and flavours similar to those of dairy products, and helps their cheeses melt better. In addition, they use local and widely available ingredients, such as melon seeds, which are a recycled ingredient from agriculture, allowing them to offer sustainable cheeses at more affordable prices.

Key results:

The ingredients are produced locally and distributed.

They provide an improvement in the cost of use in the products by reducing supply times and necessary stocks.

Disruptive innovation in the production of vegetable cheeses, improving the flavour and sustainability of the production process.

BPCE Principles

SDG Objectives

Links

<https://vacka.es/>

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost savings • Affordable prices • Innovation • Recovery and utilization of waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing problems • Organizational structures

Gimme Sabor

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Company dedicated to the development of product lines (vegetable protein, seasonings, jams, vegetable pâtés and broths) full of flavour, responsible and accessible, through plant based products by means of innovation and technology.

BPCE Principles

Key results:

They create plant-based products that taste even better than their animal-based counterparts, allowing you to cook traditional recipes without changing the taste you are used to.

SDG Objectives

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable production Positive environmental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturing process Product acceptance by consumers

Links

<https://gimmesabor.com/>

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

- <https://www.nestle.com/sustainability/waste-reduction/food-loss-waste>
- <https://www.nestle.com/sustainability/waste-reduction/actions-plastic-pollution>

Description and objectives:

Nestlé is a Swiss multinational food and beverage company. Nestlé products include baby food, bottled water, breakfast cereals, coffee, confectionery, dairy products, ice cream, etc.

Key results:

Recycles an unused by-product of malt production for the production of powdered beverage Milo. In this way, they make the most of raw materials and improve the nutrition of low-income families.

Drying technologies to help maize farmers in Nigeria reduce food waste as crops are easily attacked by pests and fungi.

Nestlé France has partnered with Too Good to Go's Eating Dates Pact to help eliminate consumer confusion around eating dates and prevent food from being discarded unnecessarily.

In Indonesia, a Nestlé factory switched from using fossil fuels to locally supplied rice husk as biofuel. In Finland, they have built a biogas-powered plant.

Use 10.5% less virgin plastics based on fossil fuels since 2018. They are eliminating unnecessary plastic in packaging and innovating so that the plastic they use is recyclable and reusable. They replace difficult-to-recycle materials with paper. They are betting on reusable and refillable packaging.

The Nestlé brand, Nespresso, has launched a new paper-based capsule that can be composted at home.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
Innovation, Emissions reduction, Green energy, Recycling waste	Access to finance, Complex process to make it circulate, High initial investments

Ingredalia

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Nutraceutical - Cosmetic

Description and objectives:

Innovative technology company founded in 2017 with the mission of creating and marketing natural functional ingredients. Specialized in the production of these ingredients from plant by-products from agri-food companies, mostly linked to the food preservation and freezing industry.

They manufacture and distribute healthy products from by-products from the agri-food sector. They are a clear example of a leading company for the circular economy, taking advantage of a fraction of biomass that currently does not have a correct valorisation.

Key results:

Works on optimizing the recovery of enzymes from broccoli for the production of its ingredient 'Sulforaphan-Smart', aimed at enhancing energy metabolism and with anti-inflammatory capabilities and improvement in well-being or the immune system. It is also making progress in the generation of alternative vegetable proteins from broccoli and other vegetables, obtaining a product similar to soy or pea protein.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recovery and utilization of waste Innovation Potential income Sustainable development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturing process Quality issues Access to finance

Location: Navarra (Spain)

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://ingredalia.net/>

Catalina Food Solutions

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

A company dedicated to the creation and production of formulations, offering complete tailor-made preparations for the food industry. They pay special attention to aspects such as taste, flavour, texture, appearance, stability, shelf life, performance, healthy eating, food safety and environment.

Key results:

They have developed a project that consists of “Increasing the shelf life of fresh fish by inhibiting histamine production”. The project has been developed with the help of the Centre for Industrial Technological Development (CDTI) of the Ministry of Industry, Economy and Competitiveness, and co-financed by the European Union (ERDF Funds) through the Operational Programme Pluriregional from Spain (2014-2020).

They work to reduce food waste through formulas that extend the shelf life of food and significantly improve its appearance, color, flavor and texture.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Sustainable development • Reduce wastefood 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality issues • Complex process

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://catalinafoodsolutions.com/know-how/>

<https://catalinafoodsolutions.com/nuevo-proyecto-de-investigacion/>

Done Properly

Location: Chile

Description and objectives:

A company dedicated to creating sustainable, innovative and healthy bio-ingredients through fermentation. An extraordinary game changer in the food industry.

Key results:

MICO is a third-generation mycelium protein, notable for its production efficiency, complete nutritional profile, and commitment to sustainability. Made with advanced fermentation technology, this mushroom mycelium-based protein uses up to 20 times less water, 150 times less land, and takes only 48 hours to produce.

RAISE is a bioprocessed ingredient that delivers umami flavour and acts as a natural flavour enhancer. Developed to improve the flavour profile of foods, it reduces the use of salt, sugar and replaces monosodium glutamate (MSG). Sourced from edible fungi and brewer's yeast, RAISE has a high umami content, a taste that generates a pleasant sensation and is associated with the perception of saltiness.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation Sustainable production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product acceptance by consumers Quality issues Manufacturing process

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.doneproperly.co/>

Biogusto

Location: Chile

Description and objectives:

Twenty-five thousand tons of rice husk accumulate each year in Chile, a waste that often ends up contaminating soils and water sources.

The interest in giving other uses to this material motivated the designer from Diego Portales University (UDP) Valentina Montenegro to develop the project “Biogusto”, packaging for food from this shell, with which it seeks replace highly polluting plastic packaging for prepared food

Key results:

Biogusto is an ecological alternative to traditional packaging, using rice husk (waste from the rice industry) as raw material. Biodegradable rice husk tableware and packaging as an alternative in the takeaway food market.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Sustainable development • Recovery and utilization of waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price volatility • Quality issues • Complex process • Useful applications of recycled materials

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.biogusto.cl/>

The valorization community

General Platforms

Location: International

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Description and objectives:

The Valorization Community (TVC) is the digital platform for the circular economy, which helps companies find applications for their industrial waste and by-products, and puts them in contact with companies interested in them, contributing to generating industrial synergy.

At the same time, they help companies that demand secondary raw materials to find new suppliers and alternative materials, and put them in contact with those who generate them.

Key results:

They are not a by-product exchange. They offer technical and commercial solutions to companies interested in the valorisation of industrial waste and by-products for commercial exchange and subsequent reuse.

The platform integrates various agents involved in the valorisation of industrial waste and by-products, including companies with technological solutions and research groups (Technological Centres and Universities) specialising in by-products and industrial waste, their applications, treatment or transformation technologies, etc.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Innovation• Potential income• Recovery and utilization of waste• Sustainable development	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Collaboration of the agents involved• Manufacturing process• Difficulty in reaching agreements• Quality issues

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://valorization.org/>

Circular Fiber

Location: Italy

Description and objectives:

Circular Fiber addresses the challenge of food waste generated by the agri-food industry by regenerating artichoke waste into nutritious vegetable flour. It aims to promote circular economy concepts by managing processing waste and converting food waste into value-added products.

Key results:

Circular Fiber has created "Karshov", a nutritious vegetable flour made from artichoke waste generated by the food industry. The solution is unique and virtuous, as it takes advantage of waste and returns value to these waste products. In addition to flour, dietary fiber is also extracted from artichoke waste.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Recovery and utilization of waste • Nutritional balance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product acceptance by consumers • Quality issues • Access to finance • Manufacturing process

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.the-arch.eu/en/solutions/circular-fiber/>

Jongerius Ecoduna

Location: Austria

Description and objectives:

This company markets in natural, highly nutritious ingredients based on algae. Its products have various applications in food, cosmetics, etc. In addition, they can be consumed as dietary supplements or be an excellent alternative for creating innovative recipes.

Key results:

Ingredients, such as spirulina and chlorella, which are nutrient-rich microalgae and naturally contain high amounts of vegan protein (40-55%). They contribute to reducing fatigue and provide natural antioxidants.

Projects: AlgaeCeuticals: A European Commission project within the framework of Horizon 2020 (Marie CurieActions). Objective: Development of proteins and natural UV sunscreens based on microalgae such as cosmeceuticals and nutraceuticals.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of new material • Innovation • Potential income • Nutritional balance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product acceptance by consumers • Raising awareness and sensitizing the population

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://jongerius-ecoduna.at/en/>

Fabumin

Location: Israel

Description and objectives:

This company develops a method to dry the cooking water from legumes until it is converted into a powder, which serves as a functional alternative to eggs for industrial applications.

This powder, like the egg, binds, foams and emulsifies. It is ideal for adding to food formulations such as cakes, biscuits, sauces, etc.

Key results:

Innovative drying technology for use in legume factories. It consists of two basic units: one to reduce the cooking water of legumes by evaporation and another to transform it into powder by drying.

Thus, 80% of the wastewater from the legumes is reusable as clean condensate water, contributing to the factory's circular economy.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Water saving • Nutritional balance • Proper water management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process design • Quality issues • Access to finance • Absence of legal standards and definitions

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.fabumin.com/>

MaGie Creations

Location: Netherlands

Description and objectives:

MaGie Creations recycles food by turning brewer's grain into a sustainable and nutritious ingredient for the food industry with its customized recycling process.

Key results:

Valorisation of brewer's grain as an ingredient with neutral flavour, good nutritional values and optimal use of resources.

Their ambition is to reduce the footprint of food production by recycling brewing grain into ingredients that are proven to deliver high taste, nutritional value and sustainability while protecting your margin.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reducing emissions Nutritional balance Recovery and utilization of waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturing process Quality issues Access to finance

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://magiecreations.com/>

Sigma Biotech

Location: Granada (Spain)

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Description and objectives:

Sigma Biotech is dedicated to the design and development of new products, working exclusively for the food industry, with all sectors. In their R&D laboratory, they are in charge of prototyping the re-design of the recipe/formulation, in order to develop a product or improve an existing one, converting the initial idea into a prototype adapted to the client's requirements, ready to be launched on the market, which streamlines the tasks and the final decision making process.

Key results:

Study of by-products, waste and/or losses from food companies for their transformation and reuse in the market, with the aim of obtaining new ingredients and/or high added value products that represent a new strategic line, and thus a benefit, for the company, at almost zero cost.

Examples of this are the extraction of nutrients derived from waste from the fishing industry and subsequently destined for supplementation and food fortification, as well as the transformation of peels, bones and other fruit and vegetable by-products into new products suitable for consumption

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation • Potential income • Recovery and utilization of waste • Sustainable development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex process to make it circulate • Manufacturing process • Design • Quality issues

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.sigmabiotech.es/aprovechamiento-y-revalorizacion-de-subproductos-de-la-industria-alimentaria/>

Mr. Broko

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Mr. Broko is a product brand belonging to Agrícola Santa Eulalia, a family business founded in 1994 and dedicated to agriculture for several generations. They currently cultivate more than 1,000 hectares of broccoli, cabbage and watermelon, which guarantees a continuous supply to their customers.

Key results:

Promotion of sustainable production and consumption of broccoli, in as many formats as possible, due to the belief in the many benefits it provides to those who consume it.

The company is currently carrying out the FIBRÓCOLIS project, the aim of which is to research the extraction and purification of food-grade fibres from broccoli waste. This initiative aims to transform the broccoli waste generated by the company into a high added-value ingredient, contributing to sustainability and the circular economy.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving • Proper water management • Recovery and utilization of waste • Recycling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient incentives • Organizational structures • High initial investments • Access to finance

Mr. Broko

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://mrbroko.com/>

Agrosevilla

Location: Sevilla (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Agrosevilla controls each of the production phases for its olives: from caring for the olive trees and harvesting the olives to manufacturing, distributing and marketing the final product, thus ensuring rigorous traceability and greater quality control during each stage of the value chain, from source to final destination.

At the moment, Agrosevilla is made up of 12 cooperative societies, representing more than 4,000 member farmers. With an annual production capacity of more than 80,000 tons of olives, we export our olives to more than 70 countries around the world.

Key results:

In the olive sector, Agrosevilla exploits an initiative for the development and commercialization of a bioactive extract rich in triterpenes which comes from by-products generated during its production, and which stands out for its anti-inflammatory qualities., anticancer and antioxidant.

In addition, the company has a total of 11,000 m² of photovoltaic panels, a project that has involved an investment of more than two million euros and guarantees a significant reduction in the carbon footprint.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving • Recovery of waste • Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance • Quality issues

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://agrosevilla.com/>

Mr. Dcoop y Biopharma Research

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Nutraceutical - Cosmetic

Location: Cordoba (Spain)/United Kingdom

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Description and objectives:

Dcoop large agri-food cooperative. It is the world's largest olive oil producer and is also a leading wine producer, as well as operating in the supply, livestock, pomace, nuts and cereal sectors.

Biopharma Research leading provider of market reports and customized research services focused on the biotechnology and healthcare diagnostics sectors.

Key results:

The collaboration between Dcoop and Biopharma Research is making progress in obtaining hydroxytyrosol, a phytochemical polyphenol with powerful antioxidant properties, which is extracted from the water used in the olive production process.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Energy saving• Proper water management• Waste recovery• Sustainable production	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Organizational structures• High initial investments• Access to finance

BPCE Principles

1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6

SDG Objectives

Links

<https://biopharma-research.com/>

<https://www.dcoop.es/>

Cerveza 'Sr. Mendrugo'

Location: Burgos (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Leading company in quality and innovation in food. Craft beer factory that follows a circular production model.

Key results:

Beer making is sustainable from the product itself, taking advantage of food that is going to be thrown away, to the packaging.

BPCE Principles

SDG Objectives

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable production Waste recovery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Price volatility Manufacturing process Quality issues Access to finance

Links

<https://mendrugobeer.com/>

Bioprocesia

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Founded in 2021, BioProcesia was created with the aim of contributing to the transition towards a more sustainable, circular, healthy and resilient animal feed. They obtain natural protein through fermentation for the production of feed (livestock, poultry, aquaculture and pets).

Key results:

Currently, common ingredients in animal feed production include soybean meal, fish meal and meat meal. The production of these involves overexploitation of limited natural resources. This demand competes with the production of food for human consumption and has a major environmental impact. BioProcesia presents an alternative method that disconnects protein production from the use of scarce natural resources. This bioprocess uses waste generated by the agri-food industry as raw material, which, through microbial fermentation, is revalued and can be reincorporated into the agri-food value chain as natural and sustainable ingredients for animal feed.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recovery of organic material • Improving the management of food by-products • Sustainable production • Reducing the carbon footprint 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational structures • Manufacturing process • Quality issues • Access to finance

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://bioprocesia.com/nuestro-producto/>

Agrain

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Denmark

Description and objectives:

In the brewing industry, starch is removed from cereal grains (such as barley, wheat or rye) to be transformed into sugars and prepared into beer. After the starch is extracted, the grains become a useless by-product and the company must manage their disposal.

However, this by-product, which is produced in large quantities, has good nutritional values and very interesting aromas for its application in new food formulations. Agrain is a startup that uses this resource that was waiting to be valued.

Key results:

Flours made from cereal grains discarded by the brewing industry. These provide nutrients (they are rich in protein and fiber), flavor and unique aromas in the recipes they include. In this way, food waste is combated, contributing to reducing emissions of CO2 and there is no need to exploit land or consume water to obtain cereal grains.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reducing emissions• Nutritional balance• Water saving• Waste recovery	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Price volatility• Manufacturing process• Quality issues• Access to finance

BPCE Principles

1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – 6

SDG Objectives

Links

<https://agrainproducts.com/>

<https://www.eitfood.eu/community/startups/circular-food-technology-aps>

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Nutripeople

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Innovative company that makes healthy snacks. It is a socially responsible food company that makes 100% natural fruit-based foods. They are committed to the circular economy to contribute to zero waste and better food redistribution.

Key results:

They take advantage of surplus fruit to create healthy, long-lasting foods. They make vitamin-rich fruit shakes enriched with proteins and antioxidants, without added sugars, to be taken anywhere. Shelf life 24 months without refrigeration.

In addition, they have reduced the plastic in their packaging by 70% and support social food projects. In one year, they have recovered 75,000 kilos of fruit, 72.5 million litres of water and reduced CO2 emissions, in 10,500 kilos.

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy savings • Recovery of by-products • Innovation • Sustainable production • Water saving • Reducing the carbon footprint 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality issues • Organizational structures • Manufacturing process • Price volatility

Links

<https://mentta.com/productos/nutripeople/?srsltid=AfmBOopODpwq3z4LFllv2J26KjfXKm5QWnB87J93IAuIV5FUGStOTmcS>

Rebread

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Poland

Description and objectives:

This startup aims to create solutions to avoid food waste. Stale bread can be transformed into a useful raw material, instead of being considered waste. It can be reused, saving resources and energy through a process that is respectful of the environment.

Key results:

They provide the bakery and retail industry with a scalable solution that simultaneously helps reduce the global problem of bread waste and provides a highly nutritious recycled ingredient with exceptional sensory qualities and multiple applications.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Innovation• Potential income• Nutritional balance• Sustainable development• Waste recovery	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Price volatility• Manufacturing process• Quality issues• Access to finance

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://www.rebread.com/eng/rebread-idea>

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Green Spot Technologies

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: France

Description and objectives:

It is a company based in France that produces and markets fermented and recycled multifunctional ingredients. Flours Ferment'Up from Green Spot combine sustainability, naturalness and quality.

Key results:

By-products generated by the fruit, vegetable and cereal processing sector are used. This contributes to reducing food waste in these industries and promoting circularity in production.

Furthermore, their fermentation processes require very little water, energy and resources. Green Spot's fermentation technology produces highly nutritious, tasty and multifunctional ingredients, achieving the goal of zero waste with the lowest possible carbon footprint.

Ferment'Up is a range of nutritious powders with good organoleptic qualities, applicable to an infinite number of recipes.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Innovation• Recovery and utilization of waste• Saving: water, energy and resources• Nutritional balance• Proper water management	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Acceptance of the product by consumers• Quality issues• Access to finance• Process manufacturing

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://greenspot-tech.com/en/>

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Insectum

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Valencia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

This company specializes in the marketing of edible insects to incorporate them into human and animal diets. As explained on their website, interest in breeding, processing and consumption of insects has grown exponentially in recent years throughout the world due to their proven nutritional components.

Insect production means reduced water and feed consumption and fewer emissions of polluting gases to produce a kilo of protein.

Key results:

The production of this type of protein has a lower environmental impact than traditional proteins. In addition, the insects feed on local surpluses, and their only waste is guano, which is used as fertilizer.

BPCE Principles

1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5

SDG Objectives

Links

<https://insectum.es/>

<https://inovalabs.es/es/5-casos-de-exito-de-economia-circular-en-alimentacion/>

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use of new material• Innovation• Potential income• Less impact environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Product acceptance by consumers• Raising awareness and sensitizing the population

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Best Practices in Circular Economy

Kaura

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Sevilla (Spain)

Description and objectives:

A family business with an international vocation, which has been dedicated to the production of processed animal fats and proteins since 1945. With more than 70 years of experience in the sector, its commitment to innovation, quality and sustainability has allowed them to become a benchmark in Spain in the recycling and revaluation of animal waste.

Key results:

They find new uses for meat that was previously waste, such as slaughterhouse products not intended for human consumption. They allow parts of slaughter animals (pigs, hens or chickens) to be converted into their smallest and most valuable unit, proteins, and also fats.

These animal wastes, so harmful to health and the environment, are transformed into fully reusable products: Fats, intended for the manufacture of biodiesel; Protein flours, for cement kilns.

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://kaura.es/>

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable development Innovation Recycling waste Potential income 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to finance Legal limitations High initial investments Recognition of secondary raw materials

Water2return

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: International

Description and objectives:

It is a project, funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme, which aims to recover and recycle nutrients by converting wastewater into value-added products for a circular economy in agriculture through the implementation of large-scale demonstration projects.

Key results:

Water2REturn treats wastewater from slaughterhouses, facilitating the recovery of nutrients that are converted into value-added products for the agrochemical industry and, consequently, for the agricultural sector, which is looking for more sustainable products that meet the increasingly restrictive requirements of legislation. At the same time, slaughterhouses solve their wastewater management problems, also reducing costs related to water consumption.

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper water management • Recovery and utilization of waste • Water saving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance • Legal limitations • High initial investments

BPCE Principles

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SDG Objectives

Links

<https://water2return.eu/es/>

AgroSingularity S.L.

Agri-food: food, agriculture, livestock and fishing

Location: Murcia (Spain)

Description and objectives:

Foodtech's Startup dedicated to the manufacture of natural and sustainable food ingredients. They replace artificial additives with 100% natural products. They transform the waste from agricultural production into powdered and sustainable ingredients, a commitment to the circular economy.

Key results:

The ingredients are produced from non-recycled plant products and by-products, fruits and vegetables, making food production sustainable.

The ingredients are produced locally and distributed. Each product has been produced at source, adding value to the entire food chain.

They provide an improvement in the cost of use of products by reducing supply times and necessary stocks.

It contributes to reducing food waste.

BPCE Principles

1 - 2 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7

SDG Objectives

Advantages	Challenges or difficulties
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cost savings• Innovation• Waste recovery	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Quality issues• Organizational structures• Recognition of by-products

Links

<https://agrosingularity.com/>

Agro2Circular: Territorial Circular Systemic Solution for the Upcycling of Residues from the Agrifood Sector

Agro2Circular (A2C) project is focused on the implementation of the first territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of most relevant residues in the agrifood sector (fruits & vegetables and plastic multilayers) into high added value products, powered by a digital tool and constructed upon a systemic approach with high replicable/scalable potential. Through this solution, A2C will face important industrial, economic & social challenges in the agrifood sector:

- 1) The fruits & vegetables (F&V) are the group of major contribution to food waste along the food supply chain rising up to > 40% of waste, and are as excellent source of natural bioactives. However, these F&V wastes are not exploited. A2C will valorise them by green routes to obtain these bioactives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods, and cosmetics.
- 2) Multilayer plastic films are widely used as industrial packaging for the protection of food and agriculture for crops due to their unique barrier properties. However, there is a lack of sorting and recycling technologies for an economic and environmentally sustainable valorisation of these multilayer structures. A2C will develop the first recycling value chain for post-industrial multilayer films based on a synergistic approach combining innovative sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination & mechanical recycling.
- 3) There is a lack of digitalisation in the agrifood sector. A2C will implement a Data Integration System (DIS) as a digital tool for ensuring traceability and as Predictive Decision Tool in the agrifood sector.

A2C will be demonstrated in the Region de Murcia (Spain) and replicable systemic solution throughout Europe for the territorial deployment of the circular economy.

Agro2Circular: Territorial Circular Systemic Solution for the Upcycling of Residues from the Agrifood Sector

Agrifood industry - food wastes

Agricultural multilayer soil - disinfection films

Multilayer aseptic bags - recycling

A2C WORK PACKAGES

REGIONAL DISSEMINATION

- Food waste upcycling in weekly local street markets
- Awareness and training to general public
- Videogame for teenagers.

Technologies for the valorization of agri-food by-products

The extraction of the compounds of interest present in the plant raw material or by-product can be carried out using a multitude of technologies, called conventional and innovative/emerging. The latter have aroused great interest in recent years since their main advantages over conventional extraction methods are that, in general, they comply with the requirements of the green process concept, where the use of toxic organic solvents is avoided or minimized, the extraction time, process temperature and energy consumption are reduced, mass transfer and extraction yields are intensified, and the integrity of the phytocomplex is preserved, especially in the presence of thermosensitive components. Furthermore, in many cases, these technologies are an energy-efficient alternative, since they allow maximum yields in a reduced extraction time (A.L.B. Dias et al. 2021).

To implement and optimize the technologies for the extraction and recycling of agri-food wastes

- i. Establishing the conditioning of agri-food waste*
- ii. Developing the optimal green hybrid extraction routes*
- iii. Purifying and stabilizing extracts for their application in new formulations*
- iv. Assessing the quality and functionality of extracts*

Technologies for the valorization of agri-food by-products

Optimal green hybrid extraction routes

AQUEOUS EXTRACTION

1:3 p/v
1 hour
98 °C

ENZYMATIC EXTRACTION

1:3 p/v
VALIDASE® TRL (0.01% of matrix)
1 hour
25 °C

ULTRASOUND-ASSISTED EXTRACTION

1:3 p/v
90 % amplitude (164 W)
1 hour
75 °C

MICROWAVE -ASSISTED EXTRACTION

1:10 p/V
EtOH/H₂O (60:40)
5000 W
7 min
60 °C

Technologies for the valorization of agri-food by-products

Purifying and stabilizing extracts

The purification processes use different mechanisms to isolate the compounds of interest. The most commonly used techniques for purification are ultrafiltration, diafiltration and adsorption-desorption processes.

Once the compounds of interest have been extracted and purified, stabilisation technologies must be applied to reduce their humidity, thus obtaining concentrated and dry products that allow their stability over time and in storage conditions that are viable for the industry. Specifically, the aim is to ensure the absence of microorganisms and to prolong the shelf life of the extracts through dehydration processes. To this end, concentration and drying technologies are used, particularly vacuum concentration, atomisation, freeze-drying and numerous drying equipment.

Packaging

After the stabilisation process, only adequate packaging is necessary, guaranteeing the food safety of the product during its shipment. Current guidelines are based on the marketing of food, ingredients, etc. in powder form.

The latest trends in the food industry are focused on the search for a Circular Economy.

To this end, the waste generated at an industrial level, for example, in the processing and transformation of fruits and vegetables, is intended to be used to obtain compounds of interest (proteins, fiber, vitamins, antioxidants, etc.) that can be added to new food formulations. In addition, the damage to the environment is minimized by using sustainable techniques, methods and technologies such as green solvents, and the energy costs of new procedures are assessed, trying to reduce them to a minimum.

There are numerous related actions that are already implemented at a Regional, National and International level, so having updated Guides to Good Practices in the Circular Economy is a tool that facilitates decision-making within the sector. In this document, a review and grouping of information has been carried out that has ranked companies that have managed to adapt to new business models, increasing their product portfolio, in first place.

This document provides key insights into the current landscape and future potential for valorizing agri-food by-products and other waste streams. The Best Practices identified serve as models for businesses aiming to adopt Circular Economy principles.

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/circular-economy_en

<https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/economia-circular/estrategia.html>

<https://carmeuropa.es/fondos-ue-murcia/programa-feder-region-de-murcia-2021-2027/#op2>

<https://www.ris4regiondemurcia.es/>

<https://planderrecuperacion.gob.es/politicas-y-componentes>

<https://transparencia.carm.es/web/transparencia/objetivos-desarrollo-sostenible>

<https://participa.carm.es/procesos-deliberativos/proceso?item=101>

RELATED WEBSITE: <https://looparm.es/casos-de-exito/>

Since October 2024, the Dynamic Catalogue of good practices in the circular economy of companies in the Region of Murcia, promoted by the Development Agency of the Region of Murcia (INFO Murcia), is also available. This is a complementary tool to the Directory prepared since it includes all companies in the Region of Murcia that want to make their circular business model visible, or entities that promote the Circular Economy for the business community.

Document available on the Agro2circular
project website publicly
agro2circular.eu

